

BREAD ROLL PACKAGING: NEW DESIGN TO SAVE FRESHNESS

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ABSTRACT

Bread is one of the most consumed food in the UAE. Usually, the bread is bought in quantities to be consumed over several days. In doing so, only the first few consumed loaves of bread are fresh while the rest keep losing freshness overtime by not tightening its seal. The aim of this project is to design packaging for the roll of bread to keep its freshness while allowing the daily consumption of bread. The results shows that the new bread packaging can provide new booming market opportunities and succeed in keeping the bread freshness.

INTRODUCTION

Many families in the UAE like to buy a loaf of bread from different bakeries because they like to eat the bread for breakfast or prepare a cheese sandwich for the school. The problem is that many customers are taking the roll of bread and losing the freshness part of other bread, where sometimes when we open the bread, it loses its freshness and taste because we may sometimes don't seal it tightly. In this project, we will design a bread roll packaging that will allow customers to take their need for the bread roll without losing the freshness of the bread. Moreover, the packing will be based on the customer's needs. If they need one or two pieces of bread for a day, they can buy each

in a sprat bag, which means we will be different from bakeries that put ten pieces in the same packaging.

STEP 1: THREE INNOVATION CHALLENGES:

1. It's a startup business. We need to have resources which means that we need financial resources (capital), manufacturing for production process, employees, land, marital, and marketing research. All of these will help us to do our product in the best way.
2. We will face a lot of competitors for our product such us other bakeries like (alarz bakery, the oasis bakery). We should provide our product to be better than the competitors.
3. The challenge is that our package will help people not lose the fresh part of the bread? Because our customer opinion is essential for us. Because our product is will run when people love it and buy it from us.

STEP 2: OPPORTUNITY TOURNAMENT AND FILTERING MODEL

STEP 2 A: WHERE TO FIND OPPORTUNITIES?

When we began our project and started doing it, we found the opportunities from three different sources: our brainstorming, customer, and our competitors in the market. We chose the best idea from our opportunity and finally put our idea for the project, “Long divided package with single bread rolls “we got our idea from the customer who is getting hard to keep the fresh part of the bread for a long time. So, our product will be keeping the bread fresh for a long time, and each customer can take the number of loaves of bread with a separate package, and it will be easy to cut. So, the people will be happy and have fresh bread.

STEP 2 B: REAL-WIN-WORTH ANALYSIS

- **Is it a real opportunity? Is this product will serve in a real market?**

Yes, because we can collaborate with ant bakery to serve our product or Bild a bakery to help our product.

- **Consider the market size, potential pricing, and availability of technology.**

Market size: the market size of our product roll package of the bread is large, and the customer demand is high, and we know that there is a different group of customers (new customer, existing customer), and the increase in other time will grow the market in the future as the graph shown:

Potential pricing: we put our price based on the competitors, so we put the price affordable to everyone so that the average price will be between 0.57 AED to 1.50AED. So, all the people can purchase our package.

Available technology: we will bring our machines and equipment and our staff to produce our product for our customers.

- **Can we deliver the product in the required volume at the required cost?**

We can offer the demand at any time with high quality, but maybe the cost will be increased for us, we will try to find a reasonable price with high quality to achieve customer need.

- **Can we establish a sustainable competitive advantage?**

Yes, our package will be different from another bakery. It will be easy to cut, and we can make a package for children and adults.

- **Can we patent or brand the idea?**

Yes, because our product is considered an innovative idea, we may trademark our brand at the trademark office. However, due to the difficulty of offering a high-quality product, we must be careful.

- **Are we more capable of executing it than competitors?**

Our capabilities are good. However, as mentioned above, we might face some issues in the production process since high accuracy is required; if we ignore it, it will affect everything.

- **Is the opportunity *worth it* financially?**

- **Do we have access to the necessary resources (financial, developmental, supply chain)?**

The necessary resources are available (monetary, sellers, market research, manufacturers, and research and development teams), but we might have difficulty finding suppliers who can provide us with the perfect roll package of bread to apply the bread on

- **Will the investment be rewarded with appropriate returns?**

A low return on investment that is not sufficient to cover our manufacturing costs is expected because consumers may disagree with the product idea; the business plan has little chance of success, profit, or return.

- **Is the opportunity *real*?**

Yes, because the customers buy the bread every day for breakfast or dinner, there are bakeries to sell the product.

- **Consider the market size, potential pricing, and availability of technology.**

Market size: the market size of our product roll package of the bread is large, and the customer demand is high, and we know that there is a different group of customers (new customer, existing customer), and the increase in other times will grow the market in the future as the graph shown:

Potential pricing: we put our price based on the competitors, so we put the price affordable to everyone so that the average price will be between 0.57 AED to 1.50AED. So, all the people can purchase our package.

Available technology: we will bring our machines and equipment and our staff to produce our product for our customers.

- **Can we deliver the product in the required volume at the required cost?**

Yes, we can serve a large number of packages to our customers at any time. It will be easy to produce it and will achieve customer satisfaction.

Due to its ease of manufacture, we would likely serve a significant amount of bread roll packages. Due to its advantages, many customers will buy our product. In turn, our financial obligations will be met.

- **Can we establish a sustainable competitive advantage?**

Yes, the package will be different. It will be easy to cut and easy to open it and the style of the package will be different.

- **Can we patent or brand the idea?**

As "roll package of bread" is considered an innovative idea, it satisfies the customers. In the end, we have the opportunity to apply for a trademark for our company name formally.

- **Are we more capable of executing it than competitors?**

This is true since we may not have to spend a lot on starting up, and our capital would be reasonable. In addition, we are the first to take advantage of this opportunity, as no other competitors are offering it.

- **Is the opportunity *worth it* financially?**

- **Do we have access to the necessary resources (financial, developmental, supply chain)?**

The necessary resources (monetary, sellers, market research, manufacturers, and research and development teams) can help us in the production process.

Our primary suppliers will be falcon factory which provides a package for many things and produce plastic cups, spoons.

Our financial capital will be from our investment and family support. If we make a success, we will look for Khalifa funds to get from them capital.

- **Will the investment be rewarded with appropriate returns?**

Yes, we may expect a good return on investment since we have a compelling product that meets our customers' expectations, giving us a long-term competitive edge that can boost profitability.

Finally, in the end, our product (extended roll package of the bread) is the best opportunity because it achieves the chance of people, business.

STEP 3: MISSION STATEMENT

MISSION STATEMENT:	
PRODUCT DESCRIPTION	We will design a bread roll packaging that allows the customers to take their need of the bread roll without losing the freshness of the other bread.
BENEFIT PROPOSITION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- easy to use. 2- save the freshness of the bread. 3- allow the customers to buy the amount of the bread roll that they need.
KEY BUSINESS GOALS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- Competitive price that allows for the sales volume and profits that are desired. 2- open our business within the next year and get profit from our business. 3- provide better customer service. 4- capture a bigger market share.
PRIMARY MARKET	-for each person who want to buy fresh bread.
ASSUMPTIONS AND CONSTRAINTS	-Housewives will like the product, because it will give them a peace of mind to not worry about the bread roll getting hard and bad.
STAKEHOLDERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1- new and existing customer. 2- Marketing and sales. 3- Manufacturing supply chain. 4- bakery. 5- Investors to invest in our product.

STEP 4: CUSTOMER NEEDS ANALYSIS.

STEP 4 A: INTERVIEW OUR CUSTOMERS

Through our view of the plastic bread bag packaging, we will work to improve for customers. by collecting the information, we want from the customer before starting any step. The main thing for the success of any product is to go to the customers and discuss with them the problem they face through the product we chose through the interview, and this is the best solution because when we go to the customers ourselves, we will see their reaction and what bothers them when using the product. But during this period, we faced a problem because of the Corona pandemic, and it is difficult for us to go and meet people through public places, and this is to ensure the safety of everyone. We reached the solution that each group member must have a personal interview with their family members or close friends. Between the ages of 15 and 60 (men and women). This interview aims to collect information and find out how people deal with the process of opening the plastic bread bag and what they encountered and drew their attention or did not like by opening the plastic bread bag packaging. And how will people feel when they open the plastic bag bread, while they are sure that the bread will not rot and become edible and that it will be fresh for a more extended period and they will not need to use preservatives or that they should eat it on the same day because they think that when the bag is opened for bread and a long period of time has passed since it remains open, the air enters inside The bag bread and changes its taste that will not be fresh and becomes inedible, and some people get rid of it. Our goal is to satisfy customers with the product and take their opinion to address their problems by producing an environmentally friendly product. The bread stays fresh for a more extended period.

Customer Quotes:

Q1: explain the process when you want to open the bread packaging. Do you face any problems when you open it and go wrong in this process?

Reem said: I wouldn't say I like the bread packaging since it takes me a while to open the tape that keeps it closed, and whenever I'm done with the bread, I need to find anything to help me keep the bread bag closed; and if not closed well the bread becomes hard.

Hayat said: The process of opening the bread package is easy. But I faced some problem when I opened the bread bag the bread flies all over the place, and the whole bag was damaged.

Meera said: I face a lot of problems when it comes to opening the packaging of something, and most of the time, I tear up the plastic bag, or sometimes I can't close it very well, so it damages the bread. Sometimes I tear up the packaging and cut the sticker date, or most of the time, it's printed on plastic, so it makes it harder for me to guess the expiration date.

Sarah said: I opened the bread tie and the tie is tough and small, and I lost it many times and then I couldn't close the package again.

Marwa said: Yes, I find difficulty in opening bread bags. I usually search for scissors or knives to open it.

Jawaher said: Yes, I do face some difficulties because I must buy a particular container to store the bread so it can last a long time, stay fresh, and prevent the bread from being moldy.

Maryam said: I open the pack, take the amount of bread I need, and seal it back. Yes, I face a problem where my kids don't close the package whenever they open it.

Hamad said: I open the pack, take what I want, and sometimes I drop the package and all the bread falls out of the package.

Nasser said: Open the package of the bread, then put the rest of the bread rolls in a box, so they don't get dry. I'm not too fond of the idea of not being able to seal the package back again.

Q2: do you think that the regular bread packaging bothers you? How?

Reem said: yes, cause it's not helpful and doesn't help store the bread correctly.

Hayat said: Yes, In my opinion it annoys me because it's made of thin bags, making the bread dry and look staler.

Meera said: Yes, it's hard to open, and it does not keep the shape of the bread.

Sarah said: No, because the style of a tie is not okay for opening and closing the package.

Marwa said: It bothers me while trying to open it as well as closing it.

Jawaher said: yes, it bothers me in a lot of ways. It's tough to close and store the package after using the bread. The package used is plastic which is unsustainable for the environment and can affect the environment in the long run, so they should come up with different creative, unique, and sustainable ways.

Maryam said: Yes because it's hard to close the package.

Hamad said: Yes, it's not worth the money for what I'm getting for

Nasser said: No, because it's so made from plastic, and it affects the environment badly.

Q3: do think that you need a product that will prevent the bread from going wrong or a product that will allow you to buy your family portion only?

Reem said that buying bread in the quantity I need will be significant since I'll be able to buy the amount that I need without having any access to bread that will go bad.

Hayat said: Yes, we need to provide another product that preserves the environment and makes our lives healthier. Having an effect that prevents the bread from going wrong will be a lifesaver. But it must be an easier way.

Meera said: I need a product that will prevent the bread from going bad

Sarah said: I want the two products

Marwa said: yes, both

Jawaher said: I would choose a product that will prevent the bread from going wrong because it's tough to estimate exactly how much your family eats. It depends, so having an effect of storing the bread is more practical.

Maryam said: I would like to have such a product; it will be lifesaving.

Hamad said: Yes, it will be helpful.

Nasser said: I think that if we have a sustainable product with the environment, it makes me happy and the second things that I need. I also want the same product to have several uses. For example, when I finish it, I can go to any bakery near me, put the bread inside the product again, and use it several times.

Many people spill drinks or food on their clothes while in restaurants, cars, or even the movies. It's hard for them to get up, clean themselves, and come back in wrinkled clothes that have just been washed. Also, people are bothered by the smell of cleaning products.

All of them faced the same problem: the difficulty in opening the plastic bag and some of the damage to the plastic bag for bread, which indicates that packaging is the main reason most of them are not satisfied with the product packaging. Because when they open the plastic bag for bread, and this may bother them a lot because the plastic bag is scattered from them and the bread falls out of the plastic bag, so they must bring the bread holders and put it inside these containers to preserve the taste and quality of the bread. Unfortunately, some keep the bag as it is and put it in its place without forcefully closing it. This may spoil the bread because it is exposed to the air and is not fresh for them. In one case when we conducted the interview, a mother who has teenage children tells us during the interview that she is upset about packing bread because of her children, because they take the bread and keep the bag for bread open, and this may bother her a lot with her as a mother because she wants to preserve her children and their health. She is distraught by the idea that her children are neglected, and at the same time, she does not want to feed her children something that is not fresh because she considers it rotten from the air and has become solid and inedible again.

On another positive side, through our interview with people, all of them are interested in obtaining an environmentally friendly product, and all of them agree that packing a bag of bread is not convenient for them and, they all agree on the point of product quality and keeping it fresh for a long time.

pictures of the problem:

During our lives as females, we must always find quick and easy solutions to make our lives easier to manage our time, because we all have those days when things don't go our way and that's why we choose helpful something because this is a problem, we face every day to prepare our breakfast, we students and mothers Those who have children should make bread for their children for school. The mother is always responsible for feeding her children what is fresh and valuable for them. That is why we chose this product to make the lives of mothers and people who make bread for themselves not take the time to fix what they did by opening the plastic bag of bread and destroying it. In this case, they must act to preserve the remaining bread. Because when we buy a bag of bread, we take it and in each plastic bag there are six or more pieces inside. Here people face the problem that when they want to prepare bread, they only use one or two pieces of bread, and the rest must be kept in a place that preserves the consistency of the bread, or they must eat it once. Our product will impress them because it will make it easier for them to open the product. Since it is environmentally friendly, they can preserve the texture of the bread for a more extended period. We can also meet customers' needs according to their desire by reducing the number of breads inside the bag to make the customer happy and gain their satisfaction to keep our product always in the forefront.

CUSTOMER NEEDS AND MARKETS

Our product is essential in every home and is made for daily use. This is all for the convenience of customers to eat bread that is well-preserved from getting anything inside. It is also environmentally friendly to be reused again and that it does not spoil in their hands when they open the product. We must have a large market size. Our product is available in all places designated for selling food products because this product is used daily, in every home, and every morning and many people consider bread as a primary meal for breakfast. Also, customers always pay attention to breakfast because it is an important meal that supports them with energy to complete their day in good health. And customers want to eat something fresh and of unique quality and benefit through packaging for bread. It is reused several times without losing the quality of the product, whether in terms of the bread being fresh or the packaging being comfortable and smooth when used. So, we focus on regular customers. However, this does not make our product any less unique or unnecessary; On the contrary, because we developed the product through customers' needs before starting to implement it. This product is unique and different from other competitors. We must win customers by creating a link in which they put their opinion, inquiries, and suggestions for us, and based on their desires. We will strive to make our product distinctive. And all this is of high quality to win customers. We have worked hard to satisfy our customers who deserve the best.

STEP 4 B: CLASSIFY YOUR CUSTOMERS' NEEDS

TYPES OF CUSTOMER'S NEEDS

STEP 4 C: LIST OF CUSTOMER NEEDS

*** The bread roll package **is easy to split (Latent Need)**

*** The bread roll package allows the right amount of bread for each family or individual

*** The bread roll package is fast to separate.

** The bread roll package is easy to use!

The bread roll package may be used under any age.

** The bread roll package **can save the bread for a long time**

** **The bread roll package is reasonably priced.**

*** The bread roll package size is priceless.

** The bread roll package is inexpensive.

** The bread roll package can be found almost anywhere.

** The bread roll package **is trustworthy:**

* * The bread roll package does not to be sealed.

*** **The bread roll package is an intelligent design**

*** The bread roll package is made of sustainable material to save the environment.

CUSTOMER NEEDS

#	The product	Needs	Importance
1	Bread roll packaging	Easy to use	5
2	Bread roll packaging	Transparency	4
3	Bread roll packaging	Affordable price	4
4	Bread roll packaging	Light weighted	3
5	Bread roll packaging	Long size	5
6	Bread roll packaging	Amount of bread in one package	5

The importance of the needs:

1. The ease of use is one of the most essential characteristics of any product that attracts customers to buy the product because it will be easy for any family member to use, whether young as three years old or an older person without any instructions.
2. The transparency of the package will allow the consumer to see the bread whether it's still fresh or gone wrong, and it also can play the role of attracting the customers to see how the bread looks like before buying it.
3. It's essential to concentrate on the price that we will set our product with because it will play a factor in the customers buying decision.
4. The lighter the weight of our package the better, because the customers always prefer to buy things that's easy for them to carry. Therefore, we will make sure to use lightweight materials in our product.
5. The longer the size of our package, the better, because that means that we will be adding more bread rolls in the package to have high customer satisfaction.
6. The amount of bread in one package will be different for each customer, where each customer has an additional amount of bread based on their need. Therefore, the design of our product must consider this need to satisfy the customers better than the other competitors.

SPECIFICATIONS “METRICS AND UNITS”

Need	The product	Metrix	Imp	Unit
1,2	Bread roll packaging	Transparency level	3	Low-high
5,6	Bread roll packaging	Amount of bread	5	Up to 15
4	Bread roll packaging	Package length	2	Cm
4,5	Bread roll packaging	Light Weighted	4	g
5,6,4	Bread roll packaging	Package width	5	Cm
1	Bread roll packaging	Time to split the package	5	Sec
3	Bread roll packaging	Unit manufacturing cost	5	AED

BENCHMARK ON CUSTOMER NEEDS

#	The product	Needs	Imp	modern bakery	luzine bakes	carrefour bakery	Oasis Bakery	Alkhayam bakers	Al arz automatic bakery
1	Bread roll packaging	Easy to use	5	•••	•••	•••••	•••	••	••
2	Bread roll packaging	Transparency	4	•••••	•••••	•••	•••••	•••••	•••••
3	Bread roll packaging	Affordable price	4	•••	•••	••	•••	•••••	•••••
4	Bread roll packaging	Light weighted	3	•••••	•••••	•••••	•••••	•••••	•••••
5	Bread roll packaging	Long size	5	••	•••	•	•••	•••	•••
6	Bread roll packaging	Amount of bread in one package	5	••	••	•	••	••	••

We have a high opportunity to improve and develop more on need number 6, the amount of bread in one package. This is because our competitors didn't satisfy the target customers need. Therefore we will direct our focus towards this need.

BENCHMARK ON METRICS

Need	Metrix	Imp	Unit	modern bakery	luzine bakes	carrefour bakery	Oasis Bakery	Alkhayam bakers	Al ARZ automatic bakery
1,2	Transparency level	3	High-medium-low	High	High	Medium	High	High	High
5,6	Amount of bread	5	Pieces	4Pieces	4 Pieces	1 Piece	5Pieces	6 Pieces	6 Pieces
4	Package length	2	Cm	21 cm	21 cm	65 cm	23 cm	23 cm	22cm
4,5	Light Weighted	4	g	50 g	50 g	125 g	52g	55g	55g
5,6,4	Package width	5	Cm	29.7 cm	30 cm	7cm	34 cm	35 cm	35cm
1	Time to split the package	5	Sec	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
3	Unit manufacturing cost	5	AED	0.75 AED	0.75 AED	1 AED	0.75 AED	0.50 AED	0.50 AED

Target specifications “Marginal and ideal values”

#M/N	Metric	Units	Marginal Value	Ideal Value
1,2	Transparency level	High-low	Medium – high	Medium
5,6	Amount of bread	Pieces	1-6 Pieces	10-20 Pieces
4	Package length	Cm	21-65 cm	22 cm
4,5	Light Weighted	g	50-125 g	125-200 g
5,6,4	Package width	Cm	7-35 cm	Longer than 50cm
1	Time to split the package	Sec	N/A	3 sec
3	Unit manufacturing cost	AED	0.50-1 AED	1 AED

The ideal value satisfies consumers while significantly affecting costs; it is more difficult to obtain than marginal value, and every organization strives for it. The excellent value is more difficult to attain than marginal value, and every organization strives for it. Answering the question of the perfect value necessitates qualitative and quantitative analysis to assess package creation while keeping costs low. We do our best to provide the most acceptable product that the consumer desires while simultaneously lowering our prices.

TRADES OFFS:

in every business, when they design for their product, there will be some conflicts between the need of the customers, the design specifications, or the cost of producing the product. Therefore, as a team, we will have to compete in either price or performance[2].

First, there is a strong positive relationship between the amount of bread and the size of the package, which means that the more bread we have, the larger the package should be. As shown in the below graph, all of our competitors (the blue dots) are the marginal values area, where they don't offer large sizes of the bread roll package.

The marginal value of the amount of bread is between 1-6 pieces, and the ideal value is 20 pieces. The size of the package in marginal value is between 7cm x 65 cm - 23cm x 35cm, and the ideal value is less than 22x190cm. We have decided to go for the ideal amount of bread and make the size of the pack = 22x190cm. These metrics are quite sufficient for an extended package.

Since we are increasing the number of bread rolls, the unit of manufacturing cost will also increase due to the strong positive relationship between them. The below graph shows how all the competitors are in the marginal zone, as they have few amounts of bread in their package, but our package will allow more portions of bread. Thus, our cost is going to be a bit higher. As the marginal value of the competitors, the manufacturing cost is 0.5-1 AED, while the ideal value is less than 1.50 AED.

THE FINAL LIST OF PRODUCT SPECIFICATIONS

#	Metric	Units	Value
1	Transparency level	High-low	Medium
2	Amount of bread	Pieces	20 Pieces
3	Package length	Cm	22 cm
4	Light Weighted	g	240 g
5	Package width	Cm	190 cm
6	Time to split the package	Sec	3 sec
7	Unit manufacturing cost	AED	1.50 AED

after a long decision making, we have decided to freeze early. The final specifications of the bread package that we will store are listed below since we want to compete on the amount of bread and the quality of the package.

In the beginning, the Transparency level of our package will be medium, where it will combine between a paper rapping and a plastic rapping. Then the package will have a length of 22 cm and a width of 190 cm. This metric will allow 20 pieces of bread in one package roll that we will be providing to the supermarkets. The weight of the package with the bread in is 240 g, which is perfect considering the amount of bread in the package. Next, the amount needed to split one bread package from the other is only 3 sec. Finally, the manufacturing cost of our package is 1.50 AED.

CONCEPT GENERATION PROCESS

The problem that we have noticed that annoys the customers the most is that when they buy bread, they are forced to buy either more or less from their family need, because of the limited amount of bread roll in each package. Moreover, it's hard to close the bread package without squeezing the package and damaging the shape of the bread. Furthermore, some family members, especially the kids, don't close back the package when they take their need of bread, and the bread gets rotten faster than it should be.

As a result, our group has developed an intelligent package that will solve these families' problems. We have developed a splitable package that will allow families to take whatever amount they need of bread. This splitable package will ensure the freshness of the other bread rolls in the package.

By analyzing the whole situation, we have decomposed the problem that the families are facing into components and their functions, and got some sub-problems:

1. the length of the package may be too short, and it may be finished quickly and may not satisfy different family needs.

2. the plastic that we are using in manufacturing the package can harm the environment.

3. The transparency level may affect the bread quality, where it may get affected by the direct light .

4. The material used (plastic) in the package may affect the teat of the bread

5. After opening the pack and closing it back, the quality of the bread is not guaranteed.

Based on the solutions that we have come up with, we have developed 5 different concepts, the table below shows the design of each concept along with its description:

CONCEPTS:

CONCEPTS	PICTURE	DESCRIPTION
Concept A:		Each bread roll will be sold individually, and the customer will buy as much as he likes
Concept B:		the bread rolls are placed on one large package, where the customers can place as many bread rolls as they need in the large package, and each bread is individually rapped.
Concept C:		A package with a zipper that allows the consumer to open the package then seal it with the zipper to protect the other bread rolls from going bad.
Concept D:		The package contains two bread rolls, which will allow the customers to consume it fast before it goes bad.
Concept E:		The package is splitable, where the customers can take as many bread rolls as they wish, and when they consume the bread, they will only take their need and the other rolls will be safe from the air and from getting bad.

CONCEPT SCREENING MATRIX

	Concepts					
	A	B	C	D	E	REF
Selection Criteria	Single bread pack	Multi individuals	Zipper bag package	Double bread roll	The splitable package	Carrefour
Easy to use	0	0	+	0	+	0
Transparency	+	+	0	+	0	0
Affordable price	+	-	-	0	0	0
Light weighted	0	-	-	0	-	0
Long size	0	+	+	+	+	0
Amount of bread in one package	0	+	+	+	+	0
Plusses	2	3	3	3	3	0
Sames	4	1	1	3	2	0
Minuses	0	2	2	0	1	0
Net	2	1	1	3	4	
Rank	3	5	4	2	1	
Continue?	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	

We agreed as a team to cancel concepts A,B,and C in favor of continuing with concept D and E.

CONCEPT SCORING MATRIX:

We will develop concept E, which got the highest total score of 4.78. therefore, we will design a package that is splittable and protects each bread roll individually.

		Concepts			
		D		E	
Selection Criteria	Weight	Rating	Weighted Score	Rating	Weighted Score
Easy to use	20%	4	0.8	5	1
Transparency	8%	5	0.4	4	0.32
Affordable price	10%	3	0.3	5	0.5
Light weighted	7%	5	0.35	3	0.21
Long size	25%	1	0.25	5	1.25
Amount of bread in one package	30%	1	0.3	5	1.5
Total Score		2.4		4.78	
Rank		2		1	
Continue?		No		Develop	

CONCEPT TESTING

THE SKETCH:

From our survey, we got the result from different people, the survey shows us that's 90% use a clip to close the bread package, and 10% of them didn't use a clip for the bread package. Closing the bread package took a lot of time for 75% of people, and 25% of them didn't take a lot of time to close the bread package. Based on our question that if they want the bread packing with medium transparency or high transparency, 70% of them like the package with medium transparency, and only a few people want the package with high transparency, that's about 30%.

Potential Sales:

The result shows us that the number of people will purchase our package is 8 people

7 of them would probably purchase the bread package.

The number of people might or might not purchase the bread package is 3

Some people would not purchase the bread package, so, the result is two

Zero number of people would definitely not purchase our bread package

Target segmentation

1. Families who have a children's that need a bread for the breakfast.
2. Individual who lives alone, and don't need a lot of bread.

Assumptions

- Families and individuals who have job.

#	Assumptions	Calculation
1	In Sharjah, each house has a family at least there is 5 people employed, in Al Gharayen there are 5 area which each area contains approximately 500	$5*5*500=12,500$
2	50% of them are working a full-time job or part-time	$50%*12,500=6,250$
3	30% of students who go to schools and universities.	$30%*12,500=3750$
4	5% didn't buy a package and eat the bread in the café	$5%*3750+6,250=$ $5%*10,000=500$ how didn't buy a roll bread $10,000-500=9500$ who buy a roll package of the bread

STEP 7 PRODUCT ARCHITECTURE

First, we do decomposition of the parts of the product:

THE ARCHITECTURE: MODULAR

Product Architecture is the organization of functional features into physical portions that serve as the foundation for a product or family of goods. There are two main categories of product architecture, integral and modular. Modular product is the relationship between functions and components and the interaction between components. Modularity in design leads to modularity in production. While an integral architecture implies complex mapping between features and functions and a high level of incidental interaction between component [4]. so, we will use Modular product architecture, which is more appropriate for our product.

We have three types of modular architecture to choose from the slot, Bus, and sectional. Slot architecture, each interface between components is different from the others, meaning that a product's various features connect be interchanged. In bus architecture, other physical features connect to a common bus component via the same type of interface is possible, which will suit our product type. Finally, in sectional architecture, all the interfaces are identical, with no single common component to which other parts attach

MODULAR ARCHITECTURE

Types of Modularity

Slot-Modular
Architecture

Bus-Modular
Architecture

Sectional-Modular
Architecture

Labeling

gives necessary information to the customers about the bread.

Paper packaging

containment and protection of the bread.

Plastic cardboard paper

it is transparent so the people will get to see the bread.

Bread packaging box

preserving the warmness of the bread.

Bread packaging bags

avoid a lot of moisture loss and keep the bread fresh.

Sticker rolls on bags of bread

Protect and safe bread from falling.

Paper box of bread packaging

People can smell the bread.

INTEGRAL ARCHITECTURE

In integral architecture, one subsystem contributes to more than one function or performed with more than one subsystem. In this way, the design will become strong and more attractive at a low cost.

To shift to a more advanced and less expensive concept, in this step, we moved the extra components that can be connected one to another or whose task can be performed by a much more vital element.

Firstly, we designed a paper packaging that can provide containment and protection of the bread, and at the same time, it will avoid losing moisture and keep the bread fresh as long as possible. Secondly, our bread packaging box that we created will help to preserve the warmth of the bread. Moreover, it will protect and save bread from falling. We designed functional bread packaging bags which can have several different functions. For example, it will avoid a lot of moisture loss and keep the bread fresh, preserving the warmth of the bread and containment and protecting the bread. Also, we come up with a unique design for our paper box of bread packaging. It will be transparent so the customer will see the bread and allow them to smell the bread.

CLUSTER ELEMENTS INTO CHUNKS:

The chunks are the packaging components that will perform various operations in the product, and the interfaces will bring the chunks together. We then assign chunks to the team and determine which pieces to outsource.

The bread roll packaging is formed of labeling that provides the customer the necessary information about the bread such as how to use it, creation date, and the expiry date+ plastic cardboard paper, which is made with transparent material to let the customer see the bread+ bread packaging bags that protecting and avoiding losing moisture to keep the bread fresh+ paper box of bread packaging allows the customer to smell the bread.

This will allow the customer to take their need for bread roll without losing the freshness of the other bread.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that creating a bread roll packaging will create a new booming market opportunity. We figured how effective our concept would be if it were implemented in the real world through the survey.

We wish that our product be helpful to the consumers, easy to use, and let them enjoy eating fresh bread at any time. Moreover, we are going to use sustainable and environmentally friendly materials. And this can assist in raising our profits.

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